

**Experiment Driven and user Experience Oriented Analytics for
Extremely Precise Outcomes and Decisions**

D3.1 Data selection, integration, and simulation services

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Abstract	D3.1 presents our progress on developing the complex analytics methods for the ExtremeXP framework, focusing on methods for dataset selection, data integration and data augmentation. This progress comprises novel research methods, code libraries and respective publications.
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				<p>of the respective sentence in Section 5.4.</p> <p>---Addressed comment <i>“Can you better elaborate on ProActive Scheduler? What does it actually do?”</i> by elaborating on the tool at the end of Section 2.2.</p>
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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
ADASYN	Adaptive Synthetic Sampling Approach
API	Application Programming Interface
ARDA	Automatic Relational Data Augmentation
BERT	Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers
CTGAN	Conditional Tabular Generative Adversarial Network
DI	Data Integration
DNS	Domain Name System
FL	Federated Learning
GAN	Generative Adversarial Network
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HTTP	HyperText Transfer Protocol
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LM	Language Model
MAB	Multi-Armed Bandits
ML	Machine Learning
MRMR	Maximum Relevancy Minimum Redundancy
SMOTE	Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique
TTP	Tactics Techniques and Procedures
UC	Use-Case

Executive Summary

Deliverable 3.1 documents the intermediate status of the core data-centric services in the ExtremeXP framework, including data selection, integration, and augmentation services. It elaborates on novel research methods that 1) automatically select datasets and augment features to improve ML training accuracy and efficiency, 2) effectively and efficiently integrate datasets by leveraging deep learning and GPU acceleration, 3) generate synthetic data to augment datasets and improve the overall accuracy of a machine learning task. The deliverable includes links to the open-source software code and libraries that implement the aforementioned services. It also documents their implementation and provides usage information.

1 Introduction

The objective of WP3 is to develop novel methods and tools to support advanced, complex analytics requirements of the ExtremeXP users during the design, execution and evaluation of an experiment. Our research focuses on: (a) methods for improving the quality and precision of training data; (b) methods that optimise and fine-tune the ML algorithms according to the users' needs and (c) methods that allow the large-scale deployment of ML/analytics workflows. The aforementioned research objectives are realized via six tasks: (i) Task 3.1: Automated dataset selection; (ii) Task 3.2: Analysis aware data integration; (iii) Task 3.3: Simulation-driven data augmentation; (iv) Task 3.4: Opportunistic constraint-aware ML; (v) Task 3.5: Continual adaptation of ML models; and (vi) Task 3.6: Scalable ML and data analytics workflow deployment on clusters/Clouds.

Deliverable 3.1 reports on the progress of the first three tasks of WP3, i.e., *dataset selection*, *data integration* and *data augmentation*. In brief, our contributions are summarized as follows:

Task 3.1: Automated dataset selection strategies and feature augmentation methods.

- We have developed methods that recommend the datasets that are ML-aware (optimized for downstream ML tasks) for the current analytics task. To this end, we have developed automated dataset selection strategies that discover, analyse, and recommend the datasets that are fit for purpose for the current analytics task. The discovered datasets and relationships can then be used for automated feature augmentation for downstream ML applications. For ML training efficiency, our method is **5 to 44 times faster than baseline and state-of-the-art approaches**.
- Our dataset selection methods utilize dataset profiles with consideration of their metadata, characteristics, semantics, and data quality, described by the meta-model. We use metadata such as Primary Key - Foreign Key pairs to utilize data structures that allow us to fully use relations between the datasets. Other metadata that we can utilize are the quantity of the intersection or the ratio of existing data. Thus, using a wide range of metadata, we can utilize a broader range of data structures, such as a graph. This, in turn, allows us to utilize metadata that was not previously used and expand into a broader range of settings.
- Our developed method can score, rank, and recommend the most suitable datasets for the given analytics and augmentation task. Our method is presented in detail in Section 3 demonstrates an **average improvement of 16% in ML model accuracy**.
- Our developed prototype provides human-readable results; the user can utilize their expertise in the dataset selection and feature augmentation process. Our system leverages the given ML model, user preferences, time constraints, and dataset statistics, and selects the subset of related datasets that contain informative features to improve the performance of the model in terms of increasing the accuracy/F1-score, reducing the overfitting risk, etc. The method developed in this task is an end-to-end ML workflow of Deliverable 3.1 that seamlessly integrates the existing dataset with newly augmented datasets, saving the users' manual effort or programming overhead. We describe our method and experiment setting in detail in Section 3.
- Our methods are available as open source on: <https://github.com/delftdata/autofeat>

Task 3.2: Analysis aware data integration and quality assurance services.

- We have extended our framework for query-driven entity resolution, QueryER [APS+25], to also work in a supervised manner, utilizing LM models like BERT, TinyBERT and DistilBERT, leveraging our previous work in [AKG20]. Our extended QueryMLER framework resulted in considerable increase in interlinking accuracy, compared to the baseline method of employing traditional similarity measures.

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- We further parallelized a significant part of our framework, allowing it to utilize GPU acceleration and achieving an order of magnitude reduction in runtimes.
- We designed the architecture and ensured component interoperability for this task, providing clear specifications to partners on our tool's characteristics. This included defining the tools' inputs/outputs, internal and external communication, and design and development requirements.
- We specified and developed a set of configuration mechanisms, that can serve as experiment variability points and will be able to capture various user preferences, constraints, and objectives. These variability points include method selection, ML model selection (for the supervised mode), similarity function selection (for unsupervised mode); LM training-specific configurations, such as class weights, learning rate, confidence thresholds etc.; Meta-blocking selection.
- We designed and developed the API that handles the initialization and communication of the tool with other components of the ExtremeXP framework.
- Our methods are available as open source on: <https://github.com/ExtremeXP-EU/QueryMLER>

Task 3.3: Data augmentation and simulation techniques.

- We have developed a Data Augmentation toolkit designed to generate an augmented dataset derived from an original dataset. Currently, the toolkit is based on a Python library. This versatile solution addresses the need to enhance the diversity and size of datasets by incorporating various state-of-the-art Data Augmentation methods, such as SMOTE, ADASYN, and CTGAN.
- We proposed a starting set of variability points. This initial set will be updated during the project. Our developed prototype is built as a Docker image with a REST API featuring different endpoints, enabling easy integration of the Data Augmentation Analytical component within the overall ExtremeXP architecture. The current development is available in the ExtremeXP shared GitLab repository.
- Our methods are available on: <https://colab-repo.intracom-telecom.com/colab-projects/extremexp/experiment-modelling/analytics-task-library/data-augmentation>

D3.1 is organized as follows: Section 2 briefly presents where the proposed methods fit in the general ExtremeXP architecture and motivates their utility via some exemplary use cases. Section 3 presents a detailed description of the methods and prototypes developed for automated dataset selection in the frame of Task 3.1. Section 4 describes the framework we developed of the efficient, scalable, and accurate data interlinking via query-driven and ML-driven techniques. Section 5 presents our methods for simulation driven data augmentation. Section 6 summarizes the key outputs of our work in WP3 and our contributions towards achieving the relevant KPIs of ExtremeXP, as well as enumerates the next step of our work.

2 Complex analytics in the ExtremeXP framework

In this section, we briefly motivate the utility of the WP3 tools for complex analytics in the context of experiment driven analytics and the ExtremeXP framework. We first provide a brief overview of the ExtremeXP architecture as presented in “D2.1 Initial architecture, languages and models for complex experiment-driven analytics” and explain how the complex analytics tools fit in. Then, we present two example use cases of the project, where various WP3 tools, combined with tools from other WPs can be exploited to improve the performed experimentation.

2.1 Complex analytics in the ExtremeXP architecture

Figure 1 provides a high-level overview of the main modules within the ExtremeXP framework. WP3 tools compose the Analytic Task Library of the ExtremeXP framework. The tools can be used by the Experiment Modelling and Experiment Execution modules of the architecture to compose and execute complex analytic workflows, respectively.

In the experiment modelling stage, the user can select one or more tools from the Analytic Tasks Library and include them as separate tasks within the experiment workflow. Further, the user can provide different configurations of these tools, such as different model hyperparameters, constraints or even data preprocessing steps that will provide the input to each task. Each different configuration is considered a variability point in the ExtremeXP framework; thus, it will create alternative workflows in the experiment execution phase.

Upon this, the experiment may be executed by the Execution Engine, which employs, among potential other tools, the selected WP3 tools. The outputs of the analytic tools, as well as user-defined evaluation metrics, can finally be visualized and explained by the respective User Interaction modules.

Figure 1: WP3 tools in the ExtremeXP architecture

2.2 An example analytics pipeline

Having a high-level overview of the framework’s architecture, we now outline a user-driven experimental workflow that allows interaction with various WP3 components formulated under the Analytics Tasks Library, providing flexibility and resource efficiency to the end-user. In this workflow, we focus on data selection, integration, and simulation, which have long been challenging issues within the analytics community.

Figure 2: Data selection, integration, and simulation services lifecycle

Figure 2 includes the proposed workflow for data selection, integration, and augmentation services. The purpose of this workflow is to guide the end-user in orchestrating the core components of the Analytics Tasks Library. This diagram shows the various experiments that the Experiment Execution Engine should recommend to the user to enhance the data wrangling processes for a specific use case. Based on the framework of resource efficiency, the engine might suggest that the user initiates a new dataset selection, where the component will select novel sources for integration using analysis-aware data integration techniques. The results of this experiment are displayed to the end-user, providing essential feedback. If the proposed experiment fails to meet the user's criteria, the Experiment Execution Engine could suggest additional tasks to expand the solution space of the use case. For instance, it might rely on data augmentation, where new samples are created based on defined policies to increase the overall accuracy and robustness of the proposed framework. Finally, if the two experiments do not align with the user’s intentions, the engine should propose more complex experiments, such as the simulation of new datasets contextualized from the previous experiments. During the aforementioned process, the complex analytics tools can be used as follows:

T3.1: Automated dataset selection. To perform dataset discovery, a user (e.g., data scientist, ML engineer) first has a base dataset to begin with, together with downstream ML tasks such as training a classification or regression model. The user can also specify parameters such as metrics (e.g., accuracy, recall, precision) through the user interface. Then, the dataset selection tool will discover,

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analyse, and recommend the datasets that are fit for the purpose of the current analytics task and automatically augment features for the given ML algorithm. To achieve this, our tool first profiles the available datasets in the data lake, describes them with a meta-model, and then calculates a score to rank the datasets. Finally, via the user interface, our tool returns a list of ranked human-readable explanations of the process; the user can also use their expert knowledge to choose which dataset can be used to augment the existing dataset.

T3.2: Analysis aware data integration. To perform data integration, the user needs to specify two data sources, particularly the URL of two CSV files. If the user wants to exploit the ML-based interlinking functionality, they also need to provide a small set of ground truth data, i.e. two data sources with explicit links between duplicate entities, so that the tool is first trained on such data (training mode). In deployment mode, the data integration tool will first deploy a highly efficient meta-blocking process which will result to minimized sets of entities candidate for interlinking. Then, it will employ the final interlinking step, which comprises either similarity matching in the unsupervised mode, or ML-driven entity matching on the supervised mode. As a result, links denoting same entities between the two data sources will be created, allowing their further utilization, e.g. by appropriately merging the two data sources, or by enriching one data source with attributes derived from the other source.

T3.3: Simulation-driven data augmentation. To perform data augmentation using the toolkit proposed in T3.3, the user needs to specify a tabular dataset with a set of features (both continuous and categorical) and a target feature, in case that the Extreme-XP user is working within a supervised ML use case. The proposed data-augmentation toolkit will compute a set of new samples, enabling exploration of whether adding synthetic samples improves the accuracy of the ML base task. Through a tailored, experimentation-driven approach, our proposed tool encapsulates a set of user-defined policies, allowing the end-user to iteratively visualize the generated samples and reduce the appearance of new potential biases in the data during the generation of synthetic samples.

T3.4: Opportunistic constraint-aware ML. The work so far under this task is to propose ML models that are aware of some constraints with the goal of enhancing the performance. Two types of constraints have been covered under two learning paradigms: supervised and unsupervised learning. In the first scenario, a constraint on the performance is expressed as a term of the model's overall loss function. Such constraint addresses the problem of imbalanced data observed, e.g., in Use Case 2: Increased Cybersecurity. The resulting algorithm is an alternative approach to traditional approaches such as over- and under-sampling to deal with imbalanced data. The proposed algorithm can also be used to enhance the quality of such traditional techniques (in two stage cascade). The second scenario pertains to clustering (unsupervised learning), where the constraint is expressed also as a loss term imposed on the topology of the data. The overall loss of the proposed algorithm, called UEC, is based on a bi-objective loss function that combines data embedding and clustering which has improved the quality of clustering compared to state-of-art techniques.

T3.5: Continual adaptation of ML models. This task's ultimate purpose is to accommodate new data when available (e.g., clustering of streaming data). The overall approach taken here is continual learning that allows us to update the model continuously. So far, the UEC has been the subject of modeling to fit the context of continual learning using a method called latent replay method, where cluster prototypes (in a latent space resulting from embedding) are continually updated. This work direction is ongoing and will be refined as the project progresses.

T3.6: Scalable ML and data analytics workflow deployment on clusters/Clouds. For many deep learning tasks, we have the extremely high cost of training the model, especially since there is a significant amount of model architectures that we can utilize. This high cost is mainly due to the cost

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of training the model from scratch in the big data and large model scenario. To combat this, we can utilize fine-tuning of existing pre-trained models as an alternative to training a model [LWZ24]. This will allow us to perform scalable machine learning utilizing the computational efforts of other users. By using the entities of datasets and models we can express the relations between the model and datasets. This will allow us to formulate the problem of inserting a new dataset to be a link prediction task. This will thus allow us to save the computational time to train the model and only need to fine-tune it to achieve the optimal performance.

To enable the scalable deployment of ML and data analytics workflows, ProActive Workflows & Scheduling by ActiveEon^{1 2} has been introduced as a potential tool to be based upon. ProActive is a comprehensive software solution for workload automation, job scheduling, and process orchestration. It offers a range of features that are highly valuable for fine-tuning and deploying machine learning models:

- **Multi-environment Support:** ProActive operates seamlessly across on-premises, private cloud, and public cloud infrastructures, enabling hybrid deployments—essential for managing the diverse computational resources required for machine learning tasks.
- **Workflow Engine:** The powerful workflow engine automates and orchestrates complex business processes, which can be used to manage the steps involved in fine-tuning pre-trained models, including data preprocessing, training, and evaluation.
- **Resource Management:** ProActive allows managers to create virtual groups of computing resources across various IT infrastructures, enabling efficient resource allocation and scaling according to the fine-tuning process requirements.
- **Self-Healing Capabilities:** Built-in self-healing mechanisms automatically detect and correct issues, ensuring continuous operation—a critical feature for long-running machine learning jobs.
- **Event-Driven Automation:** ProActive supports real-time event triggering in addition to traditional batch processing, enabling workflows to respond to events like the availability of new data or the completion of a training stage.
- **Parallel Processing:** The software enables the parallel execution of tasks, enhancing performance and efficiency, which is particularly useful for training machine learning models across multiple computing nodes.
- **ProActive Python SDK:** This SDK allows users to programmatically interact with the ProActive Workflows & Scheduling platform via Python, making it easy to integrate model fine-tuning into existing Python-based ML pipelines^{3 4} [AE3, AE4].

Integrating ProActive into Section T3.6 provides a robust and efficient framework for fine-tuning and deploying pre-trained models. ProActive handles the complexity of resource management, workflow orchestration, and fault tolerance, allowing users to focus on the machine learning-specific aspects of their tasks. Additionally, ProActive is also highly beneficial for Section T3.5, which focuses on the continual adaptation of ML models. Its automation capabilities and support for event-driven processes make it an ideal tool for managing continuous model updates in response to new data, ensuring seamless and scalable continual learning.

¹ <https://www.activeeon.com/products/workflows-scheduling/>

² <https://www.activeeon.com/products/proactive-ai-orchestration/>

³ <https://github.com/ow2-proactive/proactive-python-client>

⁴ <https://github.com/ow2-proactive/proactive-python-client-examples>

2.3 Link to the use cases

In this section, we briefly go through two of the project's use cases, analyzing them into concrete workflow steps a user can take in order to perform their experiment. Through these workflows, we demonstrate actual deployment scenarios where our tools can be exploited. We note that variations of the following workflows are being used by the consortium to build proof of concept prototypes and demonstrations of the ExtremeXP framework.

2.3.1 Use Case 2: Increased Cybersecurity

The objective of UC2 is early Multistage Real-Time Attack Detection: implementing a detection system that is aware of adversary TTPs and operates in real-time across multiple stages of an attack. By aligning low-level alerts with the high-level behaviour patterns in the MITRE ATT&CK framework, the proposed system can more effectively identify and respond to threats, thereby enhancing the organization's overall security posture.

By harnessing data-driven techniques to interpret and correlate vast amounts of security data, the ExtremeXP project, and specifically the analytical component tools, aim to contribute by proposing a framework to accurately match these low-level alerts to TTPs. So far, the following challenges have been detected in the use case, which are also recurrent in any industrial fraud and threat detection use case:

Challenge	Description	Proposed Analytical Tool
Multimodality	In this use-case, we study threat behaviour from different perspectives (data sources); thus, it is vital to determine which sources to prioritize.	Dataset Selection (T3.1)
Data Imbalance	The datasets in the domain present a high imbalance.	Data Augmentation (T3.3) Opportunistic constraint aware tool (T3.4)
False Positive Ratio	In this domain, we desire to reduce false positives for resource and time efficiency.	Opportunistic constraint aware tool (T3.4)

Table 1: Use case 2 Challenges

In detail, ExtremeXP's framework will facilitate analytical capabilities, enabling end-users to interactively define various intent-driven experimentation workflows. To demonstrate, we consider a cyber analyst in the UC2 domain. By leveraging the Dataset Selection and Data Augmentation tools, the analyst can significantly improve the accuracy of the final model. An example of how a cyber analyst might use the ExtremeXP platform is provided below:

1. User logs in.
2. User selects a labelled threat dataset.
3. User confirms the access control policy for the selected datasets.
4. User selects the intent for the current scenario, for instance suppose that the user selects the intent of classification.
5. User opens the experiment in the graphical editor and validates the proposed steps.
6. User checks the variability space of the new experiment.

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7. User clicks on start experiment.
8. User sees the experiment progress in a separate screen, this shows how the different variants are being completed.
9. At every stage of the ongoing run the user inspects intermediate results and examines them in contrast of past runs that were executed on a different intent-driven experimentation.
10. Half-way into the experiment, the user looks at the results achieved so far and have the option to rate the response (user-driven experimentation).
11. Once the experiment completes, the user is redirected to the “variant comparison” page where the metrics (e.g. prediction confidence interval) of the different variants of the experiment are compared.
12. User browses all same past experiments for comparison.
13. **User is redirected to the "experiment comparison":**
 - **The user observes that the usage of the HTTP modality does not improve accuracy, while the most contributing modalities are SMTP and DNS.**
 - **The user notices that the dataset is imbalanced, with the number of positive samples (benign samples) being higher compared to normal traffic. By using the data augmentation tool, the user adds synthetic samples to the minority class, improving the overall accuracy.**

As we can observe, using these two analytical components bridges the gap in two specific challenges in UC2: multimodality and data imbalance. The usage of the analytical tool allows for the organic selection of the best-fit modalities. On the other hand, the data augmentation component generates synthetic samples, improving the overall accuracy and the generalizability of the model in a domain characterized by highly imbalanced datasets.

2.3.2 Use Case 4: Flexible transportation analysis

The objective of UC4 (see also D6.1, Section 3.5, for details on the use case) is to perform a variety of analytics and visualizations on a transportation platforms ecosystem, where the main stakeholders/decision-makers are transportation authorities, transportation planners and modellers. These analytics are required to assess different transportation policies, using a variety of simulation software, advanced econometric modelling, or other data-driven tools.

ExtremeXP’s framework will facilitate the aforementioned analytics, by allowing the creation of intent-driven experimentation workflows, where the domain expert (e.g. Moby’s data scientist) will be able to assess variant workflows and select the optimal one, according to their intents. These variant workflows will instantiate different configurations of the MobyApp components (see D6.1, Section 3.5.2). Next, we consider a more concrete example; we note that, although several tools from WP3 are applicable in this provided scenario, we emphasize our description on highlighting the utility of the Data Integration tool.

In our scenario, the expert would like to assess the functionality of the MobyApp for *automatic mode and activity prediction*. The user can then draft the following ExtremeXP experiment:

1. User logs in.
2. **User selects a subset of the required datasets. These will include a Points of Interest (POIs) dataset, since POIs are essential for identifying a user’s activity in a specific area.**
3. User confirms usage / access control policy for selected datasets.
4. User selects intent for the current session. The intent could be a combination of prediction accuracy and efficiency (e.g. data resources, runtimes required to complete the task).

5. **User selects additional datasets, depending on the intent and the availability of relevant datasets. For example, the user initially selects the OpenStreetMap (OSM) dataset for POIs but they also have the option to draw POIs from the Google Places API (GPA).**
 - **As an experiment variability point, the user might select to obtain an enhanced POI dataset, by integrating the OSM and GPA datasets.**
6. User opens the experiment in the graphical editor and validates that the steps to be executed are the right ones.
7. User checks the variability space of the new experiment.
8. User clicks on start experiment.
9. User sees the experiment progress in a separate screen, this shows how the different variants are being completed.
10. At every stage of the ongoing run the user inspects intermediate results and examines them in contrast of past runs that were executed on a different intent-driven experimentation.
11. Half-way into the experiment, the user looks at the results achieved so far and have the option to rate the response (user-driven experimentation).
12. **Once the experiment completes, user is redirected to the “variant comparison” page where the metrics (e.g. prediction confidence interval) of the different variants of the experiment are compared.**
13. User browses all same past experiments (same intent=basic metadata, same workflow, same experimentation space, different input datasets) for comparison. Identify overfitting problems (e.g., model trained without bike thus, cannot identify bike trips). Or examine transferability of models across regions.
14. **User is redirected to the “experiment comparison” page where two or more experiments are compared w.r.t. their results.**
 - **The user can inspect the trade-offs created by employing the data integration tool. For example, they can evaluate the improvement in mode detection accuracy provided by the enhanced, integrated dataset against the increase in runtimes.**

The above experimentation scenario brings up the utility of the data integration tool in a concrete use case (UC4 – Flexible transportation analysis – Moby). Beyond this scenario, utility of employing the data integration tool has already been identified in two additional use cases: *UC1: Improvement of flash flood forecasting* and *UC3: Situational intelligence and decision making for PPDR*. These are to be further elaborated in upcoming deliverables of WP3 and WP6.

3 Automated dataset selection

ExtremeXP experiments are data centric. One of the core tasks in the ExtremeXP framework is to discover and process datasets that will eventually contribute to improve the accuracy and efficiency of the experiments. The very first step of the data selection, integration, and simulation services is to automatically discover and select the datasets for downstream ML tasks. In this section, we present our method, AutoFeat [IVB24], for dataset selection in the context of an extremely large quantity of tabular data. Given an analytics task and a data lake, there may be an extremely large collection of related data silos (datasets) beyond the original base table within the data lake that can contribute to the analytical task.

For better understanding, we illustrate the goal of dataset selection with an example. Consider the scenario that we have the task of creating a ML model to approve a loan application. We have datasets that describe applicant information, loan application information, the applicant's current and historical financial information, the applicant's previous loan history, and the asset information of previous loans. If all these datasets contain very detailed information, then there will be a very large number of features that can be used to train this model. Our goal in dataset selection is to find the datasets that contain the most useful features for the task in hand.

Sieving through the various datasets and performing feature selection is very expensive, especially in a data lake setting if there are many relevant datasets. We want to be able to automate the process of selecting the datasets and the features related to the analytics task from within these datasets. As the user, a data scientist tasked with training a machine learning model, we have a multitude of datasets and a specific task. We want to select the most relevant datasets and features from the datasets. This task has been done historically with a vast amount of manual work. Our method enables the user to automatically perform selection of the features from these datasets.

The effect of the feature selection on the ML model is unknown until the model is created. The effects of the model are purely computational and quantitative, but the users, data owners, or data scientists will have some degree of domain knowledge and expertise. To inject this domain knowledge, our method will enable multiple subsets of the datasets and features to be selected. This way, the user could incorporate domain expertise into the process. We have evaluated our method across various scenarios so that it can be applied across a multitude of different applications and that it is not restricted to a single use case. The method can thus be applied to any data lake setting for any analytics task. The above answers the fit-to-purpose aspect of the project. To provide the human-readable aspect of the method, we will provide multiple sets of features from the selected datasets so that the user will have the ultimate decision as to accept or reject the subset of datasets and features that are selected. The features will be ranked by the score that we obtained in our search process. The score will give the users an indication as to how relevant a specific set of features are. This would enable the user to determine if the selected features are indeed suitable for the intended use or purpose.

3.1 Research Contribution

In this section, we give a detailed description of our methods for feature selection over the data lake. In Section Feature Selection Workflow we will summarize our feature selection workflow and in section Automated Dataset and Feature Selection we will explain in depth our method for feature selection and evaluation methods.

3.1.1 Feature Selection Workflow

We begin by presenting general procedures for data lakes, feature selection, and model evaluation. These procedures can be utilized and combined with other tools based on the user's needs.

3.1.1.1 Data Lake

The data lake [HK123] is a fundamental building block of our approach. We have an analytical task and an abundance of data in this data lake. The data lake will have an abundant quantity of data along with a large number of data sources. To effectively utilize the extremely large quantity of data is one of the core pillars of the project. The large quantity of data sets, which all contain data features, will possibly lead to better-performing downstream ML models.

In this data lake we have organized the data as a graph structure so that the relations of the data sets are captured. Modelling our data lake as a graph, will allow the user to learn the relations between the datasets that are in the data lake. We utilize the Valentine [KS121] tool to automatically organize the datasets into a data relatedness graph. This graph can be viewed by the user, who can also interact with it. This interaction allows the user to insert domain knowledge into the workflow at this stage. Optionally, this can be achieved using tools with user-friendly interfaces like Neo4j or other graph data query and analytical tools. This enables the user to view the data lake and verify if relationships are accurately modelled. Furthermore, it allows customization of the data lake model to align with their preferences and analytical tasks.

3.1.1.2 Metadata for dataset selection

Metadata is crucial for Data Integration (DI) systems. At the core of this method, we reveal the importance of metadata, particularly data integration metadata, for ML training and inference. In the following, we divide the relevant metadata into three categories, i.e., data-related, ML-related, and hardware-related metadata. In each category, we showcase the representative types of metadata in Table 2, and discuss their roles in improving the effectiveness, efficiency, and privacy of ML model training and inference. The metadata is stored and managed by the metadata catalogue described in our model lake system [LVZ24].

Data-related metadata

Metadata in databases and data lakes refers to the information that describes the structure, and characteristics of databases or data lakes and their objects. The metadata includes information regarding schemata, statistical and descriptive data about relations and attributes, integrity constraints, silo locations, etc.

Data integration metadata

Data integration (DI) metadata refer to the information that describes the relevance and overlap between data sources, e.g., schema-level correspondences between source tables and the target table (schema mapping), and row matching between source tables (entity resolution). As our research contribution, we employ DI metadata in a threefold manner.

1. Efficiency. By representing schema mapping and row matching as matrices, Amalur facilitates a unified execution of data transformation operations and linear algebra operations, which improves the efficiency of training tasks.
2. Effectiveness. DI metadata brings new opportunities for improving the effectiveness of federated learning frameworks, e.g., through discovering the redundancy among source datasets.
3. Privacy. DI metadata leads to new challenges for data privacy in Federated Learning (FL) frameworks.

ML-related metadata

Our system Amalur not only supports efficient ML training but also manages the trained models, which makes it necessary to design a metadata catalogue that includes heterogeneous metadata for ML, i.e.,

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ML-related metadata. ML-related metadata captures the metadata from various ML lifecycle stages, such as model definition and model training. The metadata describing the model includes architecture, framework, configurations (e.g., hyper-parameters), input/output (e.g., prediction classes), etc. These types of metadata are utilized in different components in Amalur. For example, the cost estimator component in our system Amalur requires information regarding the complexity of the model (e.g., algorithm, parameters) to predict workload and model training requires hyper-parameters. The metadata catalogue also keeps track of the connections between the model and its training datasets. Thus, given a generated dataset, if a model was previously trained on this dataset, the model will be recommended to the user for inference or retraining. Besides the information describing a model, we also record the performance of ML models (e.g., model accuracy, runtime, memory footprint) under different execution environments. This information helps recommend models to users in the model preparation stage. Recommending a good model to train based on different strategies can improve the effectiveness and efficiency of ML training.

Metadata regarding hardware

The performance measurement of databases depends significantly on hardware and environment settings, which include essential details such as the number of CPU cores and memory allocation. This information is also essential for measuring ML performance during training and inference. For ML, the hardware devices may also include GPU or TPU. In general, the hardware-related metadata is regarding the execution environment in the central cluster and distributed silos. In our method, the hardware-related metadata also supports an essential component for improving the efficiency of ML training. This type of metadata, along with the data-related and ML-related metadata, supports the cost estimator to decide whether to train a model on materialized or factorized data. The result of the cost estimation results in a more efficient plan for model training or inference.

3.1.1.3 Selection Metric

Dataset selection, specifically the feature selection task is core to any ML workflow. The performance of the model is dependent on the features that the model is selected to be trained on. We perform the feature selection and data set selection using a combination of information metrics. The metrics for feature selection can be categorized under two categories; relevancy and redundancy. Metrics for relevancy include Pearson, Spearman Correlation and Information Gain and various other scores. Metrics for redundancy are metrics derived from Shannon Information such as Condition Mutual Information, Joint Mutual Information and Maximum Relevancy Minimum Redundancy. The combination of these will form the basis of our selection criteria for the datasets and features within the datasets.

The assumptions that we make regarding the datasets are that the data are heterogeneous and that the features are independent amongst the data silos. Through the selection process we can find multiple subsets of features that all optimize the metric we use. Thus, we return several different subsets of features from all the datasets with the highest score as possible features that should be selected. This is a second instance within our method that can allow users to interact with the method and inject domain knowledge into the workflow. As the user may be able to select the features that they believe to be the most informative for their purpose, or those they believe will result in the optimal model.

The feature selection tool can thus be utilized in conjunction with other tools and components. The features that are selected can then be integrated into other data science workflows, such as data augmentation and generation.

3.1.1.4 Model evaluation

When working on a single analytical task, multiple models can be utilized to achieve the same purpose. So, we benchmark all the subsets of features from the datasets with many of the popular models that

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are utilized for tabular data. The models can be split into two categories depending on the task, if the analytical task is a regression or classification task.

For regression models, commonly used algorithms for tabular data include linear regression, neural networks, K-nearest neighbours (KNN), and gradient boosting models. In classification tasks, popular algorithms include logistic regression, neural networks, KNN, decision trees, random forests, and gradient boosting trees. We can evaluate all these algorithms to demonstrate to the user which subset performs best across metrics such as accuracy, recall, precision, or F1 score.

Combining the above components, we can visualize the full workflow below.

Figure 3: Workflow and Interaction between users and dataset and feature selection

3.1.2 Automated Dataset and Feature Selection

In this section, we will provide a detailed description of our approach. Following feature selection, the primary task is ML. We can integrate this understanding into the feature selection process by leveraging the knowledge that the subsequent computational task involves an ML model. The primary goal of feature selection is to choose the most suitable features for an ML model. These models are typically trained using supervised learning techniques. Therefore, our method is tailored to optimize for this downstream analytical process. This entails incorporating objective optimization functions into the feature selection process.

3.1.2.1 Graph Construction Using Metadata

Using tools such as Valentine, we can curate and obtain dataset metadata to represent the data lake as a graph. This allows us to utilize the relational metadata between the datasets more effectively. We can thus redefine the dataset selection problem as a graph traversal problem. The metadata allows us to perform initial pruning for maintaining the quality of the features that are selected. This pruning will affect the quality of the features being selected as it will maintain the quantity of data points. Because performing join discovery and join operations can lead to a decrease on the quantity of data points that are available. With the construction of the data relatedness graph, an example of which can be seen in Figure 4, the description of the workflow of the algorithm. This will allow us to be able

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to first identify the data that are most relevant, as within the data lake there may be many datasets that are in the user's possession that may not be suitable for the task.

3.1.2.2 Feature Selection Method

Our approach hinges on the method we choose to model the data lake. The data lake is modelled as a graph where each vertex can be a dataset and each edge represents the join relation between the two datasets. This allows us to search for the optimal features by traversing the graph. In the process of traversing the graph, there are many problems to solve, such as join-able features. These are features that contain the same values or share common values. These features will be treated as keys, and in common data science workflows, keys are generally not treated as valid training features due to the high degree of uniqueness. An example of the algorithm can be seen in

Figure 4. As we traverse the graph containing all the datasets, we can take data quality aspects such as missing data or the magnitude of the intersection of the joinable features. This will allow us to maintain that the data within the datasets are relevant to the task.

Figure 4: Feature Selection Method of AutoFeat [IVB24].

As we traverse the graph, we calculate the chosen metric for automatic feature selection. The metric that we chose is maximum relevancy minimum redundancy (MRMR) which can be given in the following optimization. The task of selecting a subset of features X_i out of the feature set X can be viewed as an optimization problem. As the MRMR score is a combination of metrics that calculate the redundancy between features and the relevancy between features and the target. The target here is to identify the feature closely aligned with the user's intent. For instance, in the previous example, the intent is to develop a model capable of accurately classifying whether a loan should be approved. The target would be the attribute Y , which would be a binary attribute in the example. This will determine the quantitative relevancy between the attributes to the target. The relevancy is evaluated through

the information gain between the subsets. The relevancy score is done by maximizing the Information between the new features that we want to select and the target, minus the information between the new feature and existing features.

$$\text{Relevancy Score} = I(X_k, Y) - \beta \cdot I(X_k, X_j)$$

To measure the redundancy, the Spearman correlation is utilized. It is a non-parametric rank correlation score which measures the ranking correlation between two variables. The score is given by the equation below, where n is the number of points, and d is the distance between the ranks.

$$\rho = 1 - \frac{6 \sum_i^n d_i^2}{n(n^2 - 1)}$$

As we traverse the graph, we will begin at a base dataset and perform local feature selection. This will enable us to have a set of features that maximise the score of the local dataset. Then, traversing the graph means we will introduce new datasets. After finishing traversing the graph or finding enough features, the algorithm will stop.

Due to the selection criteria's nature, the method used to traverse the dataset graph is crucial. The order in which datasets are encountered will directly impact the sequence in which features are observed. Thus, for the calculation of the relevancy and redundancy scores, there would be an implication on the metrics as the existing set of selected features will ultimately be different. This will lead to varying sets of features being selected. The different sets of features can be ranked in terms of score for automated selection. Or to maintain a human in the loop interaction, the sets of features that are selected can be given to the user to select what they believe to be the most relevant features.

The MRMR score and Spearman correlation will be used to calculate the true score for ranking the feature to be selected as an addition to the working set of features. The final rank score will be calculated as follows.

$$\text{score} = \frac{N_{rel} \cdot \mu_{red} + N_{red} \cdot \mu_{rel}}{N_{rel} + N_{red}}$$

A final ranking score will be used to rank the features that have been selected. The score is calculated by summing the number of relevant features times the mean redundancy score and the number of redundant features times the mean relevancy score. The final score is then normalized with the total number of scores.

3.1.3 User-Interaction

We will show all the features that are selected to the user. The user, whom we would assume to be a domain expert or in conjunction with a domain expert, will then be able to select the set of features that they believe to be optimal. This would allow us to be able to combine human expertise with the data from multiple sources.

We can demonstrate this using use case 2, where the data comes from various cyber-security modes. As the task is a classification task, not all the features from all the modes will be utilized in the analytical model. So, the different sets of features from the different modes will be shown to the user and the user will thus be able to select which features they believe should be most relevant.

3.2 Variability Points

Our tool allows users to adjust the following parameters, which depend on both the model being evaluated and the dataset itself.

Similarity Threshold

- **Description:** This is the threshold from which attribute similarity is found.
- **Options:** Any real number in the range between 0 and 1, however a reasonably high value is recommended e.g. 0.6

Similarity Method

- **Description:** There are many methods upon which can be used to perform similarity searched, such as semantic or value-based similarity methods. There are also various methods that have been implemented as part of Valentine [KSI21] which is the main tool that is used.
- **Options:** COMA, Cupid, Distribution based, Jaccard Distance Matcher, Similarity Flooding.

Model Choice

- **Description:** These are the model with which the algorithm was evaluated with. These models themselves have a set of hyper-parameters that can be set depending on the exact model that needs to be evaluated against.
- **Options:** linear regression, logistic regression, K-nearest neighbours (KNN), K-means, decision trees, random forests, gradient boosting trees.

Max Features

- **Description:** This will be the number of features that are selected from the data lake given the base table. This will be bounded above by the total number of possible features to select from.
- **Options:** Any positive Integer

3.3 Evaluation

In this section we will discuss the evaluation of the tool. The tool was evaluated against two different dimensions, the efficiency and the effectiveness. The efficiency was evaluated against two baselines of ARDA and MAB. The algorithm was evaluated on a series of real-world data sets that are available on OpenML.org.

3.3.1 Dataset Description

The datasets that were used for experiments can be described in this section. The dimensions of the datasets are in Table 1.

Dataset	# Rows	#Joinable tables	# Total features	Best accuracy
Credit	1001	5	21	0.99
eyemove	7609	6	24	0.894
coverttype	423682	12	21	0.99
jannis	57581	12	55	0.875
miniboone	73000	15	51	0.9465
steel	1943	15	34	1.0
school	1775	16	731	0.831
bioresponse	3435	40	420	0.885

Table 2: AutoFeat Experiment Dataset Characteristics

3.3.2 Effectiveness Experiment

The effectiveness will be evaluated based on the accuracy of the machine learning algorithm that will be fitted based on the features that are selected. We compare the features that are selected by the

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baselines with our algorithm and then the machine learning model that is fitted based on these sets of features. However, there are some constraints on the baselines such as ARDA is limited to the search of star schemas. This is a limitation that our algorithm does not have as we can perform arbitrary discovery over a data lake and perform feature selection on the arbitrary dataset relation graphs which be in the form of any schema.

From experimentation on the datasets and models we found that our algorithm has an average increase in accuracy of 16%. This result is expected because we are not constrained to a specific schema. As we can traverse more complex schemas, we can discover more relevant features compared to the baselines like ARDA, leading to the more positive outcomes. This is what we also expect for MAB to achieve; yet our advantages over MAB are discussed below in terms of experiments efficiency.

Figure 5: Experiment results of AutoFeat on various Datasets

In

Figure 5 we have the experiment results of our method as performed on the datasets stated in

Dataset	# Rows	#Joinable tables	# Total features	Best accuracy
Credit	1001	5	21	0.99
eyemove	7609	6	24	0.894
covertype	423682	12	21	0.99
jannis	57581	12	55	0.875
miniboone	73000	15	51	0.9465
steel	1943	15	34	1.0
school	1775	16	731	0.831
bioresponse	3435	40	420	0.885

Table 2. Top: shows the efficiency of the AutoFeat algorithm compared to the baselines. The base approach is the time cost of using only the base table, so the model's performance will take a hit. Bottom: Shows the number of tables each method can join and select features from. The base approach only considers one table.

3.3.3 Efficiency Experiment

The datasets are separated into tables with known key-foreign-key constraints. The tables will then form a star schema, which is used to benchmark against the related baselines; this setting we will call the benchmark setting. The metric that will be used to evaluate the efficiency is the **feature selection time**, which is the total time taken to assess the suitability of features to be selected or not.

The efficiency of feature selection can be assessed using these criteria versus previous state of the art methods such as MAB or ARDA. These would be considered the baselines and state of the art methods to perform comparisons with. The experimentation results can be seen in Figure 6. The

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experimentation setup is utilizing different algorithms. We can see that the features that were selected using our algorithm were able to cause an increase in the performance of the model. The algorithm itself is also more efficient in terms of finding the sets of features that will lead to better performance.

Figure 6: Experiment Results of Autofeat compared to state-of-the-art methods

Based on experimentation results across multiple datasets and settings, we have demonstrated that our method can perform feature selection across a wider range of scenarios. Under comparable scenarios with state of the art methods, we achieve similar performance with higher efficiency. Due to its applicability across diverse scenarios, our algorithm has the potential to outperform existing methods in terms of model performance based on the selected features.

3.4 Installation and deployment instructions

To be able to run the workflow, the following dependencies are required to be installed:

```
Python 3.8  
Java (data discovery for data lake setting)  
Neo4j
```

After which we can download the repository from the following link:

<https://github.com/delftdata/autofeat.git>

All the pre-requisite python packages can be installed using the following:

```
pip install -e.
```

The neo4j installation will also be needed to create a graph database to ingest the data lake discovery for a representation of the data lake. A database will need to be created and started. The name of which will need to be changed in the config file within the project to the name of the database.

To be able to run the data lake discovery, the following command is used. The threshold value is a parameter that is user-defined, this is the minimum threshold for which a similarity score is accepted. This acceptance score will lead to different forms of the same data lake to be defined.

```
feature-discovery-cli ingest-data --data-discovery-threshold=0.55 --  
discover-connections-data-lake
```

After the graph version of the data lake is defined, we can run the algorithm for feature selection. The command to be used is the following.

```
Feature-discovery-cli run-tfd
```

The results of the algorithm will be saved to a "results.csv" file.

4 Analysis aware data integration

In this section, we showcase our extended tool, QueryMLER, designed for Analysis-Aware Data Integration. Building upon the foundation of our previous framework, QueryER [APS+25], and leveraging established attention-based language models for interlinking [AKG20], QueryMLER represents a significant upgrade in interlinking capabilities. Our contributions are twofold:

- We have refined the internal architecture and redeveloped various components of QueryER to support parallel processing via GPU acceleration. This optimization allows for more efficient execution of entity resolution tasks, significantly reducing processing times and enhancing overall system performance.
- We have integrated Language Model (LM) architectures for entity matching into QueryMLER to improve the effectiveness of the entity comparison and matching process. By leveraging the capabilities of these advanced models, we achieve significantly higher interlinking effectiveness, making our framework highly accurate in the task.

Interlinking, also known as deduplication or entity matching/linking/resolution (ER), is a fundamental task in data integration, aiming to **identify matching entities across different datasets**, or **clean up a single dataset potentially containing duplicates**. This task is crucial in various commercial fields such as geomarketing, navigation, and social networks. Existing literature has explored different approaches to address this problem.

In what follows, we briefly present our baseline framework QueryER, while in the next subsections we focus on the enhancements and extensions we implemented, which lead to our novel QueryMLER framework for Analysis-Aware Data Integration. QueryMLER is available in our currently internal GitLab repository ⁵, while it is periodically published as open source on GitHub: <https://github.com/ExtremeXP-EU/QueryMLER>.

Our baseline framework, QueryER [APS+25], represents a significant advancement in analysis-aware data processing, particularly in scenarios requiring exploratory data analysis. Unlike traditional approaches that apply entity techniques as a pre-processing step, QueryER incorporates data integration (interlinking) directly into the query execution process. This integration allows users to address data inconsistencies during query execution, thereby minimizing the time-to-analysis overhead. By incorporating interlinking operations into the planning and execution of Select-Project-Join (SPJ) queries, QueryER streamlines the analysis of multi-sourced, overlapping datasets while reducing overheads like schema matching. Key innovations of QueryER include the introduction of three ER-specific query operators designed for integration within query evaluation pipelines. These operators detect and resolve duplicates within tables, perform joins across multiple tables containing duplicate entities, and merge deduplicated entities into a single representation. Additionally, QueryER implements Blocking and Meta-Blocking techniques to eliminate duplicates efficiently while minimizing cleaning overhead. Unlike conventional interlinking approaches, QueryER operates directly on the data subset relevant to the user query, enhancing computational efficiency and precision in exploratory data analysis tasks.

The internal architecture of QueryER is shown in Figure 7. Initially, QueryER processes the user-input SQL query using its Query Parser, which generates an abstract query representation. The Query Planner then crafts an optimized query plan by integrating ER (interlinking) operators based on both relational and ER-specific statistics. This optimization minimizes the number of pairwise comparisons

⁵ <https://colab-repo.intracom-telecom.com/colab-projects/extremexp/data-integration/queryer>

needed. QueryER utilizes a cost-based planner that employs these statistics to place ER operators strategically, ensuring efficient query execution while minimizing overhead. Afterwards, candidate pairs of duplicate entities are identified. This phase involves a two-tier approach. First, QueryER uses Token Blocking, which maps dataset tokens to corresponding entities, identifying potential duplicates. Subsequently, Meta-Blocking [PKP+14] techniques, including Block Purging, Block Filtering, and Edge Pruning, refine these initial connections by retaining only strongly correlated entity pairs. QueryER utilizes three in-memory indices—Table Block Index (TBI), Inverse Table Block Index (ITBI), and Link Index (LI)—which facilitate rapid access to ER-related statistics and streamline the identification process. These indices are initialized and maintained in memory, enhancing efficiency by avoiding on-the-fly indexing during queries. Following the identification of candidate pairs, QueryER executes the comparison phase. Traditional string similarity functions have been initially applied to these pairs to evaluate their similarity and determine true duplicates. This process is optimized through an advanced operator pipeline, which leverages union-find data structures to minimize redundant comparisons. By checking if entities have already been matched with a common entity, QueryER reduces computational overhead and ensures high accuracy in the ER process.

Figure 7: Internal architecture of QueryER.

Our contributions in the frame of ExtremeXP focused on enhancing the identification of candidate pairs of duplicates and the comparison execution to meet the demanding requirements of handling precise analysis on extremely large datasets. Recognizing the time restraints of traditional Meta-Blocking implementations on large data, we devised novel algorithms leveraging vector and matrix operations to exploit the computational power of GPUs. By transitioning the entire Meta-Blocking process to the GPU, we achieved remarkable performance enhancements, with speed improvements upwards of 1,000% for datasets ranging from 1 to 5GB.

Furthermore, in response to concerns regarding the low recall of traditional string similarity functions, we augmented the tool with advanced techniques, particularly attention-based language models. We integrated a set of models tailored to address varying user requirements, balancing time efficiency

against accuracy. To facilitate ease of use, we engineered a pipeline within QueryMLER's query-driven architecture, enabling fine-tuning of these models on small, labelled subsets of user's data.

4.1 Research Contributions

In this section, we give a detailed description of the methods we implemented for supporting Analysis-Aware Data Integration. In Section 4.1.1, we summarize our method for performing ER techniques through vector operations. In Section 4.1.2, we summarize our approach for performing comparison execution by leveraging pre-trained language models.

4.1.1 Transferring Blocking and Meta-Blocking to the GPU

Our main tool for leveraging the computational power of GPUs are the PyTorch library's tensor classes. Tensors are multi-dimensional arrays, and PyTorch provides a range of operations for manipulating them efficiently.

For this reason, we first restructure our data into lightweight matrix formats. We achieve this by converting a conventional Block-Index Matrix, which links Blocks (B) to the Entities (E) they contain, into a one-hot encoded sparse tensor M of size $B \times E$, where:

$$M[i, j] = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if block } i \text{ contains entity } j \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

This sparse tensor employs the COO (Coordinate Format) storage scheme, where memory is allocated only for coordinates containing non-zero numerical values, assuming that the rest are zeroes. Typically, for a matrix to be considered sparse, less than 33% of its elements should be non-zero. This characteristic aligns perfectly with the ER problem, as, on average, less than 1% of the $B \times E$ Block-Index Matrix is populated.

In the COO format, memory storage comprises of a 2-dimensional index tensor representing the coordinates of non-zero values (*nnz*), and a 1-dimensional tensor of the same size containing the numerical values corresponding to these coordinates. In our scenario, this 1-dimensional tensor is populated with ones.

With the data formatted appropriately, we move on to the Meta-Blocking task. We remind that Meta-Blocking enhances a collection of blocks (B) by eliminating redundant comparisons while retaining relevant ones. This process involves two main methods: block refinement and comparison refinement. Block refinement consists in Block Purging (BP) and Block Filtering (BF), where BP removes oversized blocks that lack distinctiveness based on a predefined threshold, while BF retains entities in the smallest blocks based on a specified percentage. Comparison refinement includes Edge Pruning (EP), which minimizes unnecessary comparisons by transforming the block collection into a graph where entities are nodes and co-occurring pairs are edges. EP assigns weights to edges and prunes those below a specified minimum score.

Below we offer an in-depth explanation of how each of these methods was adapted to be implementable with tensor operations. In our implementation, we made use of the `torch.cuda` and `torch.Tensor` libraries of PyTorch for Python. Our experiments were run on a system with CUDA GPU GeForce RTX 4090.

Block Purging

Given the sparse matrix M , Block Purging is performed by executing basic vector operations as such:

- Sort the rows of M based on the sum of their elements along the rows dimension. This involves computing the row-wise sums and storing them in a new vector S of size $nnz \times 1$, followed by sorting S . Then, create a dictionary that maps each sorted row sum to its original index position before sorting. Finally, define a vectorized mapping function that takes the X-axis positions of M (denoted as $M.rows$) as input and returns a new vector of indices based on this dictionary. Note that this sorting operation does not alter the y-axis of M (denoted as $M.columns$), preserving the original order of entities for further operations like comparison execution.
- Once M has been sorted, we execute Comparisons-Based Block Purging with a smoothing factor sf , which defines the threshold for the BP operation, through vector operations as follows:
 - Split vectors S and M from the top, keeping $m\%$ of their rows. This is done since Block Purging typically removes a small uppermost number of blocks and as such, we can begin by assessing smaller batches of the Block Index until we find the number of blocks where the breaking condition is satisfied.
 - Calculate the comparisons inside blocks by mapping the function $f(N) = \frac{N!}{2}$ to vector S , producing the vector S' .
 - Calculate the levels of blocks by finding the unique instance counts of vector S , producing the vector L .
 - Produce the vectors S'_o and L_o by performing a right shift on the corresponding vectors.
 - Calculate the vector $(L \circ S'_o - sf \cdot L_o \circ S)$ and find the position of the first negative value. If found, cut from M all rows up to that position from the top. If not found, repeat for the next $m\%$ of rows.

Block Filtering

Block Filtering aims to reduce the number of unnecessary comparisons in M by removing every entity on the matrix from the $k\%$ biggest in size blocks which contain it. To achieve this with vector operations, the following steps are performed:

- Determine the removal threshold T_i for each entity i along the columns of M . This can be achieved by computing the reduced sum of each column, multiplying the result by $k\%$, and rounding down. The resulting vector T of size $1 \times E$ represents the removal thresholds.
- Compute the set of elements to remove. This is accomplished by performing a "sparse" cumulative sum operation on M along its columns. For each element $e = (i, j)$, its value is updated to the sum of its own value and the previous non-zero value in the same column. This operation is performed by:
 - Identifying the unique elements of the vector $M.columns$ and counting their occurrences.
 - Creating a dictionary cd where the unique elements are keys, and their values are initialized to 0.
 - Defining a nested function that takes an integer i as input, retrieves the current cumulative count from $cd[i]$, increments $cd[i]$, and returns the previous cumulative count.
 - Mapping the nested function to each element of $M.columns$.

The resulting modified matrix M_f holds, for each element (i, j) , the number of larger blocks than B_i that entity j is in.

- With T and M_f ready, a vectorized filtering of M_f is performed. This involves applying T as a step function along the rows of M_f . For each element (i, j) of M_f , the step function S is applied:

$$S(i, j) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } value(i, j) \leq T[j] \\ 1, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Figure 8: Block Filtering performed on a 6 x 5 matrix with a filtering parameter $k = 50\%$. The steps are as illustrated: I. Compute the reduced sum along the column axis. II. Compute the scalar-vector product of the resulting vector with the filtering parameter k illustrates an example of Block Filtering performed on a 6 x 5 matrix.

Figure 8: Block Filtering performed on a 6 x 5 matrix with a filtering parameter $k = 50\%$. The steps are as illustrated: I. Compute the reduced sum along the column axis. II. Compute the scalar-vector product of the resulting vector with the filtering parameter k

Edge Pruning

Edge Pruning represents the final and most computationally intensive step of Meta-Blocking, necessitating the utilization of GPU acceleration. This process typically involves transforming the Block-Index Matrix into a weighted, undirected graph, where entities serve as nodes and edges signify their correlation strength.

The weights of these edges can be determined using a variety of weighting schemes, but generally rely on the number of common blocks between pairs of entities. Subsequently, low-weight edges are pruned to retain only the most significant connections. The number of connections to retain is defined by the variable $k_threshold$, which, in our implementation, equals the number of non-zero values in M after filtering.

To execute this operation efficiently on the GPU, sparse matrix multiplication is employed. Specifically, given the one-hot encoded sparse matrix M , the product $M^T \cdot M$ yields a matrix Q of size $E \times E$, where element (i, j) denotes the number of common blocks between entities i and j .

As the multiplication can lead to an explosion in non-zero values, making Q impractical to store entirely in GPU memory for large datasets, the process is performed in batches. For each batch, a specific number of rows (entities) are retained in M^T , and the matrix multiplication with M is executed.

Cardinality-Based Edge Pruning is performed with vector operations as such:

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- For each batch, keep only the entities relevant to the current batch of size *batch size* by applying a mask on M^T 's indices and values vectors, such that:

$$i \leq M^T.rows \text{ and } M^T.rows < i + batch_size$$

- Perform the matrix multiplication of the batched M^T_{Batch} with M to obtain Q_{Batch} , representing the number of common blocks between entities within the batch and all other entities in the matrix.
- Remove the entities of the current batch from M to free up memory.
- Retain only the relevant connections of the batch by applying a mask on Q_{Batch} 's indices and values vectors, such that:

$$\begin{aligned} i &\leq Q_{Batch}.columns \\ &\text{and} \\ Q_{Batch}.columns &< i + batch_size \\ &\text{and} \\ Q_{Batch}.rows &> Q_{Batch}.columns \end{aligned}$$

- Compute the cardinality weights of edges using the formula:

$$\begin{aligned} common_blocks &= \frac{Q_{Batch}.values}{no. \text{ of blocks}} \\ \log_term_i &= \log_{10} \frac{common_blocks}{column_sum[Q_{Batch}.rows]} \\ \log_term_j &= \log_{10} \frac{common_blocks}{column_sum[Q_{Batch}.columns]} \end{aligned}$$

$$Q_{Batch}.values = common_blocks * \log_term_i * \log_term_j$$

- Retain only the top *k threshold* values of the result set, along with the corresponding entity pairs.
- Repeat until all entity connections have been computed. After calculating the top *k* lists for each batch, unite all lists and retain only the top *k threshold* values from the combined list. This ensures correctness as the top *k* values of the entire graph will have been retained after examining every batch.

Figure 9 illustrates an example of the matrix multiplication performed wholly and in batches on a 6 x 5 matrix.

Figure 9: Edge Pruning performed on a 6 x 5 matrix. Top: Creation of Q through the multiplication of M^T with M . Bottom: Creation of Q_{Batch} through the multiplication of M_{Batch}^T with M .

4.1.2 ML-Assisted Comparison Execution

To refine the comparison execution sub-task, we have utilized advanced neural network architecture by integrating attention-based language models into our framework, building on the paradigm of our previous work [AKG20] on interlinking. This approach allows us to capture more informative and contextually relevant similarities between entities. Attention-based neural networks, particularly Transformer models, excel in interlinking textual entities by focusing on the relevant parts of the input data. This enhances the network's ability to understand and link contextually similar entities. Unlike traditional unsupervised similarity metrics like Jaccard similarity, which rely on straightforward text comparisons, attention mechanisms provide trainable parameters that can capture useful patterns appearing in the data under deeper contextual analysis. This improved performance is crucial for managing the complexity of named entity interlinking task, as these networks can attend to important features within names and their contexts across different datasets.

In this supervised scenario, our tool operates in two main modes: training and deployment. First, users provide a (small) dataset with known duplicate entities and their ground truth links for the training phase. The system fine-tunes a pre-trained attention-based model, such as DistilBERT [SDC+19] or TinyBERT [JYS+20], on this dataset to learn specific representations and characteristics of the entities. During this phase, pairs from the ground truth are designated as true matches, while the remaining pairs are labelled as false, improving the model's capacity to recognize subtle similarities. The training phase involves configuring model hyperparameters and storing the fine-tuned model for later use.

During the deployment phase, the trained model is used to identify duplicate entities in new datasets. Users input one or two new datasets, and the system performs query-driven entity resolution to generate potential candidate pairs. The fine-tuned model then takes as input these pairs to determine if they represent the same entity. This process ensures high accuracy in linking the same entities across

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different sources. The output is a set of links between matched entities, which can be used for further data integration tasks, such as merging datasets or enriching one dataset with attributes from another.

We support two BERT [CT19] variants: DistilBERT and TinyBERT. DistilBERT, a compressed version of BERT, retains much of the original model's performance while being faster and more memory-efficient, making it ideal for general use cases. In our experiments, DistilBERT achieved comparable precision to BERT while requiring less computational resources, making it our default model for entity resolution tasks within QueryMLER. TinyBERT, optimized for resource-constrained environments, offers a compact architecture suitable for rapid fine-tuning and inference. This makes it particularly beneficial for scenarios requiring quick data exploration and short input-to-output cycles. Users can choose between these models based on their specific needs, balancing precision, recall, and computational efficiency.

The architecture of our tool is illustrated in Figure 10, comprising the Data Integration Engine and the Language Models Engine. The Data Integration Engine processes queries through the Experimentation Engine, while the Language Models Engine interacts with Knowledge Management to retrieve and store necessary data. Users input their query alongside a subset of their dataset and provide corresponding ground truth values of truly duplicate pairs within that subset. The Data Integration Engine first executes a highly efficient meta-blocking process to minimize the sets of candidate entities for interlinking. The Language Models Engine then performs the final interlinking step, either using similarity matching in unsupervised mode or LM-driven entity matching in supervised mode. The module's output is a deduplicated (clean) dataset, which is returned to the Experimentation Engine for further use. This comprehensive workflow ensures that our tool can effectively handle both supervised and unsupervised scenarios, providing high accuracy and efficiency in data integration tasks.

User intents are transliterated to a set of hyperparameters, which can be tuned accordingly through our tool's API. These parameters are as follows:

- `model`: Type of pre-trained model.
- `epochs`: Number of passes over the dataset.
- `batch_size`: Number of samples processed per iteration.
- `learning_rate`: Rate of parameter updates.
- `max_seq_length`: Maximum length of input sequences.
- `evaluation_metric`: Measure of model performance.
- `confidence_threshold`: Threshold for predictions.
- `top_k_predictions`: Number of top predictions to consider.
- `class_weights`: Weights for different classes.
- `loss_func_type`: Type of loss function used.

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Figure 10: QueryMLER's internal architecture

4.2 Implementation Information

The QueryMLER tool is implemented with Java and Python and is served as an API. More information for how to install and run the tool can be found on the sections ahead.

4.2.1 Installation

Java 17 and Python 3.10.10+ are required. Information for installing Java can be found on this link: <https://www.oracle.com/java/technologies/downloads/>. For installing Python, one can visit: <https://www.python.org/>.

One's system must also possess Apache Maven for the tool to be compiled. For information regarding its installation, one can visit: <https://maven.apache.org/install.html>.

To check the versions installed in their system, one can run the following commands:

```
$ java -version
```

```
$ python --version
```

```
$ mvn --version
```

One should start by downloading the latest version of our source code. If git is installed, this step can be implemented as follows:

```
$ git clone [https://colab-repo.intracom-telecom.com/colab-projects/extremexp/data-integration/queryer]
```


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This will create a folder named QueryER which holds the project's source code. The framework is configured through the `config.properties` file, which includes the `model.json`, containing the schema (the database that points to the data). In its current implementation, **the `datapath` in `model.json` must be changed** to the user's equivalent directory.

For the section of the tool implemented with Python, it is recommended to use a virtual environment, which will host all necessary libraries, as follows:

```
$ python3 -m venv <path/to/new/virtualenv/>
$ source <path/to/new/virtualenv/>/bin/activate
```

Now, with the virtual environment activated, one can proceed to install the required libraries. The required libraries are:

- pandas – 2.2.0
- torch – 2.2.0
- pyarrow – 15.0.0
- numpy – 1.26.3
- scikit_learn – 1.4.0
- transformers – 4.37.2
- random – 1.0.1
- matplotlib – 3.8.3

4.2.2 Deployment instructions and options

To create the jar file, one can run:

```
$ mvn package
```

To run the jar file, one can run the following command on the console:

```
$ java -jar ./target/queryER-API-2.0.0.jar
```

This instantiates the query execution engine's API. If the user wishes to perform supervised entity resolution by fine-tuning and inferring a language model, the language models' server must also be instantiated. To do this, one can move to the `bert_module` folder and run:

```
$ python3 llm_server.py && model_api.py
```

Once the system has been set up, the API can be called for model fine-tuning or for inference. Below we provide example bodies for the API POST requests. *Italicized* hyperparameters are optional.

For fine-tuning a model:

```
url = "http://localhost:5000/train"

data = {
    "dataset" : "dsd/publications.csv",
    "dataset_name" : "publications",
    "ground_truth" : "data/ground_truth_publications.csv",
    "query" : "SELECT DEDUP * FROM oag.publications",
    "train_df_name" : "train_candidates",
    "model_name" : "./my_model",
```


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```
"tokenizer_name" : "./my_tokenizer",
"model" : "distilbert-base-uncased",
"epochs" : 1,
"batch_size" : 32,
"learning_rate" : 0.001,
"max_seq_length" : 128,
"evaluation_metric" : "accuracy",
"confidence_threshold" : 0.5,
"top_k_predictions" : 3,
"class_weights": [1.0, 5.0],
"loss_func_type": "CrossEntropyLoss"
}
```

For inference:

```
url = "http://localhost:5000/inference"

data = {
  "dataset" : "dsd/publications.csv",
  "query" : "SELECT DEDUP * FROM oag.publications",
  "model_name" : "./my_model",
  "tokenizer_name" : "./my_tokenizer",
  "batch_size" : 32
}
```

4.2.3 Variability Points

In our QueryMLER tool, there are several parameters and configurations that can be adjusted to tailor the behavior and performance of the system. These parameters allow users to customize the entity resolution process according to their specific requirements and constraints. Below is a list of variability points along with their descriptions.

Comparison Execution Function (model)

- **Description:** Specifies the type of pre-trained language model to use for entity resolution tasks.
- **Options:** BERT, DistilBERT, TinyBERT.

Epochs (epochs)

- **Description:** Determines the number of passes over the dataset during the training phase of the language model.
- **Options:** Any positive integer value representing the desired number of epochs.

Batch Size (batch_size)

- **Description:** Defines the number of samples processed per iteration during training or inference.
- **Options:** Any positive integer value indicating the desired batch size.

Learning Rate (learning_rate):

- **Description:** Controls the rate at which the parameters of the language model are updated during training.
- **Options:** Any positive real number representing the learning rate.

Maximum Sequence Length (max_seq_length):

- **Description:** Sets the maximum length of input sequences processed by the language model.

- **Options:** Any positive integer value indicating the maximum sequence length.

Evaluation Metric (`evaluation_metric`):

- **Description:** Specifies the measure used to evaluate the performance of the language model.
- **Options:** Accuracy, F1-score, Precision, Recall, or any other appropriate evaluation metric.

Confidence Threshold (`confidence_threshold`):

- **Description:** Establishes the threshold for accepting predictions made by the language model.
- **Options:** Any real number between 0 and 1 representing the confidence threshold.

Top K Predictions (`top_k_predictions`):

- **Description:** Determines the number of top predictions to consider during inference.
- **Options:** Any positive integer value indicating the number of top predictions to consider.

Class Weights (`class_weights`):

- **Description:** Assigns weights to different classes during training to address class imbalance.
- **Options:** A list of real numbers representing the weights for different classes.

Loss Function Type (`loss_func_type`):

- **Description:** Specifies the type of loss function used during training of the language model.
- **Options:** CrossEntropyLoss, MeanSquaredError, BinaryCrossEntropy, or any other appropriate loss function.

4.3 Evaluation

In this section, we evaluate with respect to efficiency and accuracy of interlinking. To gauge the flexibility of our architecture, we included several splits of the datasets for fine-tuning and testing. Section 4.3.1 contains a detailed description of the datasets that we used, and Section 4.3.2 contains our experimental evaluation results.

4.3.1 Evaluation Datasets

For evaluating our methods, we used datasets containing duplicate entries, known as "dirty" datasets, consisting of bibliographical data and toponyms. Regarding the first, our experiments were conducted on two main datasets: **Publications**⁶ and **Papers**⁷. The Papers dataset was tested with two sizes: one with 1 million entities and another with 5 million entities. For the toponyms dataset, we utilized **geographical data for the United States of America**⁸. To fit our use-case, we expanded the dataset to introduce duplicates, by generating new rows of data based on the alternate names column of the original data. We note that the toponym dataset fits directly to the purposes of use case 4 (Flexible transportation analysis and visualization), where interlinking of different sources for place names could increase the quality of the data and consequently, the quality of the analytics and the developed models. Further, interlinking of geospatial entities can also benefit use cases 1 (Improvement of flash flood forecasting thanks to the use of AI) and 3 (Situational intelligence and decision making for PPDR).

A detailed description of the datasets is given in Table 3.

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⁶ <https://dblp.org/faq/How+can+I+download+the+whole+dblp+dataset.html>

⁷ <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/project/open-academic-graph/>

⁸ <https://www.geonames.org>

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Dataset	Description	Source	# Rows	# Columns	# Duplicates
publications	Contains bibliographical data of academic publications.	dblp.org ¹	67K	4	5K
papers	Contains bibliographical data of academic publications.	Open Academic Graph ²	1M, 5M	18	15K, 350K
toponyms	Geographical data.	geonames.org ³	550K	3	64K

Table 3: QueryMLER Experiment Dataset Characteristics

The algorithm for populating the dataset with duplicates is described below.

Input: df: DataFrame (input data, containing the Pol's names, alternate names and the state code) duplication_threshold = 0.9: integer (variable for figuring how many entities will be duplicated) similarity_threshold = 0.5: integer (variable for figuring which alternate names will produce duplicates)	
Output: new_df: DataFrame (the new, dirty dataset) gt: DataFrame (the ground truth, which contains the id pairs of duplicate entities)	
1	Initialize gt as an empty DataFrame
2	Initialize new_df as a copy of df
3	For each row of df, if row['alternate names'] is not 'NaN' and length(row['name']) > 15: a. For alt_name in row['alternate names'][:2], if random.random() (a randomly generated integer in the range [0, 1]) is lesser than duplication_threshold: i. If alt_name ≠ row['name'] && length(alt_name) > 15 && cosine_similarity(row['name'], alt_name) ≥ similarity_threshold: (a) Append the new_row = [alt_name, row['alternate names'], row['state code']] to new_df. (b) Update gt with the id pair of row and new_row.

Algorithm 1: Algorithm for populating the toponyms dataset with duplicates.

We note that the state code column of the dataset was not accounted for during the experiments and was kept only as metadata for dividing the data into buckets.

4.3.2 Results

Our evaluation metrics aimed at highlighting improvements in terms of inference time and result accuracy. We have included metrics that show the performance of our research contributions analysed in Section 4.1. With regards to Section 4.1.1, we compared our approach with the baseline of a standard Meta-Blocking implementation on the CPU, and for Section 4.1.2, we compared our method with the baseline of the standard Jaccard similarity measure for string matching.

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For inference time, we measured the duration in seconds required for inference of both sets of results. For accuracy assessment, we employed the metrics of Sensitivity (True Positive Rate or Recall) and Specificity (True Negative Rate), which are defined as so:

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Negatives}}$$

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{\text{True Negatives}}{\text{True Negatives} + \text{False Positives}}$$

Dataset	Method	TP	FP	Time (seconds)
Publications 67k Entities 5,347 Duplicates	CPU Meta-Blocking	5,306	307,827	~0
	Vectorized Meta-Blocking	5,298	306,961	~0
Papers 1 Million Entities 15,314 Duplicates	CPU Meta-Blocking	14,855	4,111,534	180.8
	Vectorized Meta-Blocking	14,861	4,112,203	17.6
Papers 5 Million Entities 341,647 Duplicates	CPU Meta-Blocking	273,318	45,553,000	5286
	Vectorized Meta-blocking	273,186	45,552,085	209
US Toponyms 63,560 Duplicates	CPU Meta-Blocking	47,993	499,998	~0
	Vectorized Meta-Blocking	42,851	503,540	~0

Table 4: Results for Meta-Blocking performed on the CPU and the GPU.

In Table 4, we demonstrate runtimes required for the Meta-Blocking operations to be performed either on the CPU (baseline) and through vector operations on the GPU (our contribution). The key takeaways are the following:

- Regarding accuracy, both implementations perform similarly with regard to True Positive and False Positive values found, which proves the correctness of our algorithm. The differences observed in the numerical values are attributed to the different programming languages used for each implementation.
- Regarding time, the implementation running on the GPU shows great scalability based on dataset size. More specifically, for the smaller Publications and US Toponyms datasets, both implementations perform extremely well. However, for the larger Papers datasets, our new implementation showcases improvement of at least **one order of magnitude**.

Dataset	Method	TP	TN	FP	FN	Sensitivity	Specificity	Time (seconds)
Publications 67k Entities 5,347 Duplicates <small>Models fine-tuned on ~20% of the data Tested on a query of ~70% of the data</small>	Jaccard	3,425	140,653	74,326	257	0.930201	0.6542639	4.3
	DistilBERT	3,603	212,121	378	79	0.9785443	0.9982212	851.8
	TinyBERT	3,579	212,072	427	103	0.9720261	0.9979906	83.3
Papers	Jaccard	1,221	591,342	259,722	1,831	0.4000655	0.6948267	32.6

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1 Million Entities 15,314 Duplicates <small>Models fine-tuned on ~5% of the data Tested on a query of ~30% of the data</small>	DistilBERT	2,922	850,040	1,024	130	0.957405	0.9987968	7,034
	TinyBERT	2,712	850,073	991	340	0.8885976	0.9988356	681
	Jaccard	26,046	207,898	292,100	21,947	0.5427041	0.4157977	4.1
US Toponyms 63,560 Duplicates <small>Models fine-tuned on data for the state of California</small>	DistilBERT	41,523	495,881	4,117	6,470	0.8651887	0.991766	1088
	TinyBERT	37,115	498,902	4,638	10,878	0.7733419	0.9907892	97.5

Table 5: Results for comparison execution performed with Jaccard, DistilBERT and TinyBERT.

In

Dataset	Method	TP	TN	FP	FN	Sensitivity	Specificity	Time (seconds)
Publications 67k Entities 5,347 Duplicates <small>Models fine-tuned on ~20% of the data Tested on a query of ~70% of the data</small>	Jaccard	3,425	140,653	74,326	257	0.930201	0.6542639	4.3
	DistilBERT	3,603	212,121	378	79	0.9785443	0.9982212	851.8
	TinyBERT	3,579	212,072	427	103	0.9720261	0.9979906	83.3
Papers 1 Million Entities 15,314 Duplicates <small>Models fine-tuned on ~5% of the data Tested on a query of ~30% of the data</small>	Jaccard	1,221	591,342	259,722	1,831	0.4000655	0.6948267	32.6
	DistilBERT	2,922	850,040	1,024	130	0.957405	0.9987968	7,034
	TinyBERT	2,712	850,073	991	340	0.8885976	0.9988356	681
US Toponyms 63,560 Duplicates <small>Models fine-tuned on data for the state of California</small>	Jaccard	26,046	207,898	292,100	21,947	0.5427041	0.4157977	4.1
	DistilBERT	41,523	495,881	4,117	6,470	0.8651887	0.991766	1088
	TinyBERT	37,115	498,902	4,638	10,878	0.7733419	0.9907892	97.5

Table 5, we demonstrate the interlinking effectiveness results, measured on the final, comparison execution step, comparing the Jaccard string similarity function (baseline) and the language models-driven matching, using either DistilBERT or TinyBert. The key takeaways are:

- Regarding accuracy, the language models significantly outperformed the baseline Jaccard method on both Sensitivity and Specificity. Particularly, the language models contributed heavily to decreasing the number of False Positives, while simultaneously increasing the number of True Negatives found. DistilBERT outperformed TinyBERT, especially on the Papers and US Toponyms datasets. In most cases, the implemented language model based interlinking achieves almost ideal interlinking accuracy, especially regarding the specificity metric.
- Regarding time, the language models proved slower than the baseline string matching method. On average, TinyBERT was one order of magnitude slower than Jaccard, and DistilBERT was one order of magnitude slower than TinyBERT.

5 Simulation-driven data augmentation

In this task, a toolkit is proposed to generate synthetic data to augment datasets and improve the overall accuracy of a machine learning task. While data augmentation is a conventional technique in the community, it must be applied carefully to ensure that biased samples are not introduced into the trained models [MJP15]. In this section, the research contribution is detailed, introducing the proposed method and outlining the contribution to ExtremeXP.

5.1 Research Contribution

Synthetic data generation has received special attention in recent years, especially with the emergence of novel generative algorithms such as LLMs or GAN models. However, the high complexity of these models often obscures the intrinsic means of determining potentially biased samples. To this end, previous methods have been proposed to minimize synthetic biased samples in data augmentation workflows. A promising approach introduced in [FCX21] for image data augmentation begins with defining a set of predefined policies. In this context, policies are predefined transformations that modify the data in concrete ways to create synthetic samples, such as rotation, translation, or scaling. These policies are then randomly combined to create more complex policies. Each merged policy is assigned a weight based on the importance of each augmented sample in the training process of a proxy task. This adaptive weighting prioritizes the most relevant policies, thereby creating more effective augmented samples. Another promising approach is [RZY22], which involves gradient optimization of the policies within the main classification network. For example, a policy in an image dataset might involve colouring the output image. In this approach, the policies are constrained by distributional characteristics and feature correlations.

Figure 11: Simulation-driven Data Augmentation

Taking advantage of the ExtremeXP framework, an experimentation-driven methodology has been developed. It is based on determining a set of user-defined quality policies that are interactively refreshed through various experiments. This allows for the reduction of biased synthetic data and highlights regions with high uncertainty, recommending that the user runs new simulations to gather additional data. In detail, our proposed methodology, conceptualized in Figure 11, is based on taking a labelled tabular dataset and a set of policies as input. It then proposes new synthetic samples using different Data Augmentation Algorithms. In each iteration, it asks the user for new feedback (update policies), allowing for the modification or creation of new policies. This iterative process ends when it is determined that the new synthetic samples meet the expected quality (using the Quality Assessment component), returning the newly generated synthetic dataset.

5.1.1 Policy qualification using an experimentation-driven approach

Determining high-quality policies depends on the context of the user and prior domain knowledge. The policy is primarily composed based on user expectations and causal relationships tied to a particular knowledge domain. To this end, we relied on taking advantage of the ExtremeXP approach, conceptualizing the data augmentation task using an experimentation-driven approach, allowing users to interactively provide feedback by defining new policies for each proposed experiment. An example of a policy in use case 2 is to augment data only for users with an *http_200_ratio* less than 0.60. This approach targets users whose HTTP logs frequently indicate errors. The policies can be more complex, such as targeting users with an *http_200_ratio* < 0.60 & a *DNS_protocol_tcp* > 0.2. This ensures precise creation of synthetic data, allowing users to easily assess the augmented data and policies. If the augmented samples do not meet user expectations, the policies can be adjusted in the next iteration of the experiment

Figure 12: Conceptual overview of the Data Augmentation process

5.2 Methodology

To build the stated data augmentation framework, two different methodologies are conceptualized: the Greedy Approach and the Inner Quality Approach. The Greedy Approach is based on a post-processing filtering method that filters out generated samples which do not meet user-defined policies. This approach is tested using linear interpolation algorithms such as Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) or Adaptive Synthetic Sampling (Adasyn) [[HBA08][NWL02]. The second approach, named the Inner Approach, involves encoding a set of policies directly within the loss function and relies on deep learning algorithms, such as Conditional GAN (CTGAN) for the synthetic data generation [NWL02]. After obtaining the various synthetic samples, it is proposed to visualize the augmented samples, which will allow assessment of the data quality. If the quality criteria are not met, the user can interactively determine a new set of policies, enabling the execution of further experiments based on these new policies.

5.2.1 Data Augmentation Strategy A: Greedy Approach

The procedure starts by splitting the training data into mini-batches, each represented by D_m^{train} . The augmentation process, described in pseudo-code format in Figure 13, begins with generating an initial set S using function F_1 on the first mini-batch, where F_1 is defined as the Augmentation Algorithm. The core of the method iterates by selecting random mini-batches and applying the nested function

transformation F_2 . F_2 refers to the filtering operation which generates a set of new synthetic samples meeting q policies. These policies are defined interactively using human knowledge, and S is updated if the newly generated S' demonstrates greater similarity with D^{val} . This iterative process refines S until it reaches a feasible solution.

The total number of buckets is determined using the following heuristic: given N as the size of the minority class, the number of buckets is set as $B = \left(\frac{N}{0.10 \cdot k}\right) \cdot k$, where k is a parameter that allows the adjustment of the total number of buckets considered. We refer to this procedure as greedy because it computes a solution space that is higher, and it is curated using a post-processing approach.

```

procedure GreedyDataAugmentation():
   $S \leftarrow F_1(D_1^{train})$ 
  while  $S$  is not a complete feasible solution do:
    Select random  $\langle D_1^{train}, D_2^{train}, \dots, D_M^{train} \rangle$ 
     $S' \leftarrow F_2(F_1(\langle D_1^{train}, D_2^{train}, \dots, D_M^{train} \rangle, q))$ 

    IF  $\text{similarity}(S' \cup S, D^{val}) \leq \text{similarity}(S, D^{val})$  do:
       $S \leftarrow \{S' \cup S\}$ 

  return  $S$ 

```

Figure 13: Pseudocode for the Greedy Approach

5.2.2 Data Augmentation Strategy B: Inner quality

This approach takes advantage of algorithms that converge on a loss function, incorporating a set of specific policies or constraints, and directly maximizing accuracy compared to the Greedy Approach. For example, if the end-user defines a policy to maintain a certain level of diversity in the age feature, this approach adds a diversity term to the loss function, which penalizes a lack of variance among the generated samples. Technically speaking, the Conditional Tabular Generative Adversarial Network (CTGAN) is formulated using a discriminator (\mathcal{L}_D) and a generator (\mathcal{L}_G) containing their own loss weights. For the generator, it includes policy-specific loss.

Generator Loss: $\mathcal{L}_G = \mathcal{L}_G' + \mathcal{L}_P$

Discriminator Loss: $\mathcal{L}_D = \mathcal{L}_D'$

Loss function \mathcal{L}_G and \mathcal{L}_D [LSC19]. The \mathcal{L}_P represents the policy-specific loss. Intuitively:

Loss Policy: $\mathcal{L}_P = \sum_k^{k=0} |\text{policy}_k(G(x') - x_k)|^2$

where x represents the real data and x' the augmented data.

5.2.3 Quality Assessment and Visualization

Finally, the quality assessment module allows for the visualization of the new synthetic data generated and facilitates the extension of new policies. A proposed visualization for the component is presented in Figure 14 which displays two datasets with continuous features F1, F2, F3, and F4. Here, "D" refers to the original dataset, and "D'" refers to the synthetically generated dataset. This visualization enables us to compare the two distributions and propose new policies based on their distributional

properties. During this task, new visualizations and user interactions will be refined, allowing for the refinement of more granular and complex properties.

Figure 14: Visualization aspect of Data Augmentation Toolkit.

5.3 Evaluation

This section includes an initial experiment to validate the contribution of the proposed approach. For evaluating our methods, three different open-source datasets are used to propose an empirical validation of the approach. Dataset 1 is the breast cancer dataset, containing a total of 569 samples with 30 unique features. Dataset 2 is the wine dataset, with a total of 178 samples and 13 different features. Dataset 3 corresponds to the iris dataset, another classical dataset for evaluation, with 150 samples and 4 different features. All the datasets are formulated as tabular datasets with a binary target feature. Table 6 and

Pairwise	SMOTE		ADASYN		CTGAN	
	Mean	Var	Mean	Var	Mean	Var
Dataset 1	0.043	0.0026	0.001	0.00064	0.027	0.0011
Dataset 2	0.26	0.002	0.24	0.00009	0.054	0.00009
Dataset 3	0.069	0.014	0.05	0.012	0.012	0.004

Table 7 present the performance evaluation of the standard data augmentation methods (SMOTE, ADASYN, and CTGAN), used as ground truth information for later comparison, using three different datasets (wine, iris, and cancer datasets). Each experiment was conducted 100 times, and the mean and variance of the performance metrics were reported. The experiments used a random train-validation split, with the train and validation sizes set to 0.2.

	SMOTE	ADASYN	CTGAN
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Wass	Mean	Var	Mean	Var	Mean	Var
	Dataset 1	13.03	0.07	12.02	0.02	25.93
Dataset 2	5.84	0.09	20.33	0.03	13.01	2.29
Dataset 3	0.12	0.0076	0.31	0.0025	0.05	0.012

Table 6: Data Augmentation experiments using Wassertein distance

Pairwise	SMOTE		ADASYN		CTGAN	
	Mean	Var	Mean	Var	Mean	Var
Dataset 1	0.043	0.0026	0.001	0.00064	0.027	0.0011
Dataset 2	0.26	0.002	0.24	0.00009	0.054	0.00009
Dataset 3	0.069	0.014	0.05	0.012	0.012	0.004

Table 7: Data Augmentation experiments using Pairwise correlation

Our ongoing evaluation of the greedy approach is based on studying the number of iterations needed to converge the similarity between the synthetic samples generated in each split and the validation split (as in the previous experiment, a validation split with a size of 0.2 was used). In this experiment, the criterion for including new synthetic samples in the final synthetic dataset (defined in Figure 9 as $S \leftarrow \{ S' \cup S \}$) is based on selecting those instances where the distance between the validation set and the samples is in the first quartile.

Figure 15: From left to right relationship between distance and number of iterations using SHAP and Adasyn techniques.

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Figure 15 illustrates the relationship between the number of iterations and the average similarity to the validation set. As observed in the first figure, from left to right, which corresponds to using SHAP as the base data augmentation technique, the methodology converges to a stable similarity (using the Wasserstein distance) after approximately the fourth iteration. On the other hand, using ADASYN, as shown in the second plot, the plot becomes stable after approximately the sixth iteration. Compared to using SHAP, ADASYN requires a higher number of iterations to converge, and the range of distances with the validation dataset is higher.

5.4 Data Augmentation toolkit architecture

The stated library is delivered using a microservice with a Docker and a REST API interface, allowing easy integration into the ExtremeXP architecture and interaction with different variability points, as described in Section 5.4.1. To deploy the data augmentation, in Section 5.4.2 we state a set of instructions to set up the Docker container, which exposes an API containing the set of functionalities.

Figure 16: Data Augmentation Toolkit Architecture

The experimentation engine communicates with the Data Augmentation module using the REST API interface, see Figure 16. The Experimentation Engine initiates a new data augmentation experiment with specific variability points and provides a path to the dataset (the DataStore to be used is yet to be determined). The Data Augmentation core interacts with the DataStore to request the specified dataset via the API and passes it to the Data Augmentation engine. The result of the data augmentation is stored in the DataStore, and the user receives an identifier for the newly generated dataset.

5.4.1 I/O and current variability points

Inputs:

- Link to a tabular dataset
- Set of Variability points

Outputs

- Link to the tabular dataset

Variability points:

- Option selection: {Toolkit, Greedy, Inner}

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- Learner selection (IF Toolkit): {SMOTE, ADASYN, CTGAN}
- Hyperparameters: {i: number of iterations, n: generated samples}
- Similarity function: {Wasserstein Distance}

5.4.2 Deployment instructions and options

To deploy the data augmentation toolkit, follow these steps to set up the Docker container, which exposes an API containing the set of functionalities stated in the previous section:

1. Clone the repository. First, you need to clone the repository containing the data augmentation toolkit. Open your terminal and execute the following commands:

```
$ git clone git@colab-repo.intracom-telecom.com:colab-projects/extremexp/experiment-modelling/analytics-task-library/data-augmentation/policy-based-data-augmentation.git
$ cd policy-based-data-augmentation
```

2. Build the Docker image. The docker image contain all the necessary dependencies and the code to run the toolkit.

```
$ docker build -t policy-based-data-augmentation .
```

3. Run the Docker Container. This container expose its functionalities through an API.

```
$ docker run -p 5000:5000 policy-based-data-augmentation
```

4. The API documentation with the different exposed endpoints is defined in <http://localhost:5000/docs> after running the Docker container.

Alternatively, the following instructions set up the deployment environment (assuming a clean python3 installation):

1. Create the Virtual Environment

```
$ python3 -m venv myenv
$ source myenv/bin/activate
```

2. Install the required packages

```
$ pip3 install -r requirements.txt
```

3. Start the Jupyter notebook

```
$ jupyter notebook
```


6 Conclusion

This deliverable presented the outcomes of WP3 regarding data selection, integration, and augmentation services during the first period of the project, while putting complex analytics in the context of the ExtremeXP framework. The main achievements of the presented work can be summarized via the following tangible outcomes:

-
- The data discovery tool, AutoFeat, is available online: <https://github.com/delftdata/autofeat>
- The data integration tool, QueryMLER, is available online: <https://github.com/ExtremeXP-EU/QueryMLER>
- The data augmentation framework is available on: <https://colab-repo.intracom-telecom.com/colab-projects/extremexp/experiment-modelling/analytics-task-library/data-augmentation>
- A series of papers have been published or pending publication in high rank venues:
 - AutoFeat: Transitive Feature Discovery over Join Paths, ICDE'24 (T3.1)
 - Data lakes: A survey of functions and systems, TKDE'23 (T3.1)
 - Amalur: Data integration meets machine learning, ICDE'23 (T3.1)
 - QueryER: A Framework for Fast Analysis-Aware Deduplication over Dirty Data, EDBT'25 (To be Published) (T3.2)
 - Policy-Based Data Augmentation, Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery (To be Published) (T3.3)
 - Besides research talks over ICDE 2023 and 2024, we have also organized yearly international workshops on databases and machine learning (DBLM) in 2023 and 2024, which further bring interested researchers and practitioners together.

Finally, in the following table, we summarize our progress with respect to all KPIs relevant to WP3 (complex analytics), demonstrating that we have already satisfied various of our set targets, according to our initial planning.

KPI	Description and target	Progress
2.1	Decrease by 20% of user manual work and by 25% of computational overhead compared to the state-of-the-art data integration tools.	QueryMLER achieves high interlinking accuracy requiring fine-tuning on just the 5% of the evaluation dataset. Further, it achieves significant decrease in manual effort since (automated) interlinking accuracy surpasses 95%.
2.2	Increase the performance (e.g., accuracy) of ML and analytics workflows by 10%	QueryMLER increases interlinking accuracy by more than 60% in two different datasets, with respect to baseline interlinking via string similarity measures. For ML training efficiency, AutoFeat is 5 to 44 times faster than baseline and state-of-the-art approaches. AutoFeat , demonstrates an average improvement of 16% in ML model accuracy.
3.1	Increase of accuracy of algorithm and model selection methods by at least 10%	Planned for D3.2

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	compared to the state-of-the-art methods.	
3.2	Steady increase of precision of the selection strategies because of continual learning.	Planned for D3.2
3.3	Increase of ML model performance (higher accuracy and precision, lower risk of overfitting) by 20% compared to the state-of-the-art feature augmentation methods.`	AutoFeat achieves a 16% higher model accuracy using feature augmentation. Which is a 24% increase over the previous state of the art.

Table 8: Progress on relevant KPIs

Following the delivery of the initial research methods, system architecture, and core functionalities, WP3 technologies and tools will be evaluated against existing use case requirements and considered for testing deployments at selected use case sites. The components will continue to evolve, taking into account the results of other technical work packages as well as the evolving requirements and constraints of the use cases.

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